

HOW DOES SOCIAL MEDIA EXACERBATE FEELINGS OF INADEQUACY AND SOCIAL COMPARISON AMONG YOUNG ADULTS: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

This review examines how social media use can lead to feelings of inadequacy among young adults (17-27) in their romantic relationships. People tend to compare themselves to the seemingly perfect online lives of others, leading to lower self-esteem and depression. The review highlights gaps in research on how social media affects broader self-concept and downward comparison (comparing oneself to those worse off). Social media literacy education and platform-specific effects are suggested as areas for further study. Finally, the review emphasizes the importance of understanding cultural differences in how people experience social media.

Key Words: Social Media, Young Adults, Social Comparison, Self-Esteem, Mental Health, Social Media Literacy

Introduction

In the annals of psychological research, few phenomena have captivated scholarly attention in the digital age as much as the advent and proliferation of social media (Przybylski et al., 2013). This literature review delves into the impact of social media on feelings of inadequacy and social comparison among young adults between 17-27 years, particularly in the context of unresolved emotions stemming from romantic relationships. The culture of self-presentation and the highly tailored design of these platforms have burgeoned a unique digital environment in which young adults incessantly engage with curated content that often belies the complexity of real life (Chentanaphop & Van den Bulck, 2021). As this medium for self-expression and communication has grown, so too has the propensity for pervasive social comparison, not only affecting young adults' social interactions but also gravitating their sense of self-worth around virtual feedback loops (Liu & Yuan, 2018). Consequently, this literature review serves as a crucial foundation, illuminating the current state of knowledge and boldly setting the stage for an innovative research question that seeks to unravel the dynamics between the use of social media and psychological well-being.

The Social Comparison Theory

The concept of Social Comparison Theory, introduced by social psychologist Leon Festinger in 1954, asserts that human beings possess an intrinsic drive to evaluate themselves, often in comparison to others. This seminal theory hypothesized that individuals determine their social and personal worth based on how they stack up against others they perceive to be within the same reference group (Festinger, 1954). In the age of social media, Festinger's foundational principle takes on new dimensions. The omnipresent nature of online platforms acts as a catalyst for incessant social comparison, with young women habitually measuring their achievements,

appearances, and lifestyles against the meticulously curated personas of their peers (Chen et al., 2016). This digital era's amplification of Festinger's theoretical framework reveals how social media is not merely a tool for social connectivity but a complex environment for constant evaluation and comparison, thus maintaining a significant resonance with the central tenets of Social Comparison Theory within the contemporary social media landscape (Van den Berg et al., 2018).

The 'Highlight Reel' Effect

The phenomenon of social media's "highlight reel" effect, wherein users encounter and engage with selectively curated portrayals of others' lives, constitutes a potent catalyst for upward social comparison and associated feelings of inadequacy (Baker & Sinclair, 2021). This curated presentation, often comprised of peak moments and noteworthy achievements, fosters an environment where young adults view these highlights as the standard rather than the exception. Przybylski et al. (2013) illuminate this process by suggesting that the well-edited and meticulously selected nature of social media content can lead to users perceiving their own lives as comparatively lacking, impacting subjective well-being negatively. Complementing this, Hunt et al. (2018) empirically substantiate the link between the frequency of social media use and increased feelings of social inadequacy. They propose that the curated nature of content users are exposed to inflates perceptions of others' quality of life, thus warping self-perception and intensifying feelings of insufficiency.

Algorithmic Amplification and the Echo Chamber

The issue of the "highlight reel" effect is further exacerbated by the intricate entwinement of social media algorithms with user experience. These algorithms are designed to captivate attention by curating content that appeals to individual preferences and behaviors, as noted by Van Dijck

(2013). However, this personalization can inadvertently foster environments that are ripe for upward social comparisons. Algorithms selectively filter content, frequently favoring posts that depict success, beauty, and affluence, which can provide a skewed impression of what is considered a societal norm. This reinforcement of predominantly positive and exceptional experiences can lead to an "echo chamber" of idealized lives, exacerbating feelings of inadequacy among young adults (Van den Berg et al., 2018). They are often left in the throes of a relentless pursuit of matching an illusory standard set by the algorithmically amplified highlight reels of their peers. This tailored experience disregards the random, less polished, or everyday aspects of living, fundamentally distorting users' perceptions of reality and potentially intensifying feelings of self-doubt and inadequacy (Przybylski et al., 2013).

Social Media Engagement and Self-Esteem

The dynamic relationship between social media engagement and self-esteem has been subjected to rigorous empirical scrutiny, with a growing body of research illuminating the detrimental impact this relationship can have on an individual's self-worth (Przybylski et al., 2013). Kraus et al. (2017) present compelling evidence that the propensity for social comparison engendered by social media participation is correlated with diminished self-esteem. This decrement in self-esteem is hypothesized to be an outcome of the continuous juxtaposition of one's everyday life against the meticulously cultivated personas displayed on social networks (Brown et al., 2018). The frequency of interaction with these idealized representations does not merely serve as a gentle backdrop; rather, it actively shapes self-appraisal processes, promoting a sense of inferiority and a skewed internalization of personal success benchmarks. This transformation in self-esteem through social media has grave implications, as self-esteem is a cornerstone of psychological well-being (Rosenberg et al., 1995). The repetitious encounter with profiles that portray peers as perpetually

successful or joyous, compounded by the inherently comparative nature of social media, siphons away from the sense of individual accomplishment and can lead to a pernicious cycle of relentless self-critique and validation-seeking behaviors (Chou & Lee, 2017). While the prominent narrative suggests that social media platforms are mere tools for connection, the evidence posited by Kraus et al. (2017) calls for a reconceptualization of these digital platforms as potential catalysts for a self-esteem conundrum, particularly amongst young adults whose identities and self-concepts are still in flux (Lenike et al., 2018).

Mental Health Repercussions

The engrossing nature of social media is not without its mental health repercussions. Prolonged engagement with social networks has been empirically associated with an increase in symptoms of anxiety and depression, particularly among young adults who are in a formative stage of developing their identities (Lenike et al., 2018). This phenomenon has been subject to substantial research, with studies such as those by Chentanaphop and Van den Bulck (2021) providing insights into the psychological toll that unrelenting social comparison can exact. Through a careful analysis of user behavior and reported well-being, their research highlights how the fear of missing out (FOMO) acts as a catalyst for persistent checking of social media platforms, which in turn exposes individuals to innumerable opportunities for negative self-evaluation. The omnipresent nature of perfectly curated lives on social media, juxtaposed with one's own perceived inadequacies, may contribute to a relentless cycle of mood deterioration and anxiety, laying the groundwork for depressive episodes (Przybylski et al., 2013). Such findings suggest a complex relationship between social media use and the mental health of young adults, underpinning the necessity to further decipher the underlying mechanisms of these psychological outcomes.

Social Media Use and Self-Esteem

While the relationship between social media use and self-esteem is well-established, there is a pressing need to broaden our understanding of how these digital interactions shape a more holistic self-concept among young adults (Lin et al., 2019). Self-concept encompasses not only one's self-esteem but also perceived competencies, interpersonal abilities, and the multifaceted sense of self that an individual holds (Shaffer & Chandler, 2013). Existing literature falls short in addressing how, precisely, social media platforms contribute to or detract from a young adult's appraisal of their skills and social acumen. For instance, persistent exposure to others' achievements and social successes may not only lower self-esteem but can also lead young adults to question their abilities to achieve similar milestones or foster the same quality of relationships (Chou & Lee, 2017). Furthermore, the performative nature of online interaction, where users curate their online personas, raises questions about its influence on users' perception of their authenticity and social dexterity in offline contexts (Przybylski et al., 2013). This deficiency in existing literature signals the need for a meticulous examination of the ways social media use interacts with the larger constellation of self-concept domains. Understanding these dynamics is critical as they have the potential to affect young adults' real-world decision-making, goal-setting, and capability to form and maintain meaningful relationships (Lenike et al., 2018). Therefore, future research must aim to fill this gap, integrating self-concept theory with social media research to better inform interventions that could mitigate the potential adverse effects of online socializing on young adults' broader perception of self.

Social Media and Downward Social Comparison

While the majority of research within social psychology has focused on the consequences of upward social comparison on social media, downward social comparison, a potentially mitigating

factor, remains an understudied area with significant implications for young adults' emotional well-being (Van den Berg et al., 2018). In scenarios where individuals compare themselves to those seemingly worse off, the expected boost in self-esteem and alleviation of inadequacy might not always materialize in the digital context (Gibbons & Buunk, 2017). Curated online portrayals of hardship and vulnerability, often accompanied by an outpouring of community support and affirmations, might paradoxically lead some young adults to perceive a lack of support in their social networks or a belief they are not navigating challenges as effectively as their peers (Haidt, 2016). This dearth of robust research on the intricate dynamics of downward social comparison on social media exposes a crucial gap in the current literature. This gap hinders our comprehension of its multifaceted effects on feelings of inadequacy and necessitates a deeper exploration of how these processes might influence, either positively or negatively, the psychological struggles young adults face in the digital age (Cheng et al., 2019).

Social Media Literacy

Amid concerns about social media's influence on young adults' psychology, social media literacy emerges as a crucial factor with the potential to mitigate negative effects (Livingstone et al., 2020). Social media literacy equips individuals with the critical thinking skills necessary to navigate the online world, fostering discernment amidst the waves of content and unrealistic portrayals (Das & Puri, 2019). This includes the ability to critically evaluate the curated nature of online presentations and the manipulative power of algorithmically driven content (Marwick & Boyd, 2014).

However, research on the effectiveness of educational interventions designed to enhance social media literacy remains in its early stages (Livingstone et al., 2020). While initial studies suggest that programs educating users about the mechanics and intentions behind social media platforms may help reduce social comparison (Huang et al., 2019), there is a dearth of robust long-term

studies evaluating the efficacy of these programs (Livingstone et al., 2020). Critical questions remain unanswered: Can social media literacy interventions consistently mitigate feelings of inadequacy among young adults? If so, what are the essential components of an effective literacy program? These unanswered questions highlight a significant gap in the literature. A systematic investigation into the long-term benefits of social media literacy education is urgently needed. Equipping young adults with these critical skills can empower them to counter the disillusionment fostered by the seemingly perfect lives displayed online and cultivate a healthier relationship with social media.

Platform-Specific Effects

To fully comprehend the impact of social comparison on young adults, it is essential to consider the distinct characteristics of each social media platform (Przybylski et al., 2013). For instance, text-based platforms like Twitter may trigger social comparison by exposing users to praise and cleverness, causing them to question their intellectual abilities or conversational skills (Valdes et al., 2012). In contrast, Instagram's emphasis on images often highlights physical appearance, ideal lifestyles, and material possessions, potentially leading to body image dissatisfaction and reduced life satisfaction (Jackson et al., 2018). This makes image-centric platforms more potent drivers of social comparison when compared to text-based ones due to their immediate and emotional impact. Despite this, there is limited research into these platform-specific effects (Huang et al., 2019). Therefore, it's crucial to understand how different social media platforms uniquely influence young adults' well-being. For example, although there is a hypothesis that Instagram's focus on visuals fosters a stronger environment for upward social comparison (Jang & Kim, 2020), robust empirical evidence to support this is lacking. Researchers must analyze the distinct cultures of each platform

and their specific influences on young adults' feelings of inadequacy to tailor social media literacy interventions and usage recommendations (Livingstone et al., 2020).

Cultural Considerations

While the significant and growing recognition of social media's impact on mental health is undeniable, contextualizing these effects within diverse cultural frameworks is imperative (Hofstede, 1980; Triandis, 1995). Cultural values and norms significantly influence how individuals interpret and respond to social comparison triggers encountered online. For instance, in collectivistic societies where the emphasis lies on community and social harmony, the experience of social comparison on social media may differ from that in individualistic cultures, where personal achievement and self-promotion are more highly valued (Chen et al., 2011). In cultures that prioritize interdependence, social media narratives that glorify individual success might lead to a distinct form of social comparison, potentially causing feelings of inadequacy due to a perceived lack of contribution to the collective good. Conversely, in individualistic societies, social media platforms may intensify competition and the pressure to excel, potentially inflating the standards by which users judge themselves against others (Gu et al., 2020).

This cultural variation represents a critical lens that warrants further scholarly exploration. It has the potential to reveal culturally specific coping mechanisms and the need for targeted interventions that acknowledge the cultural underpinnings shaping social media use and its associated psychological effects (Moreno et al., 2021). Understanding these nuances can inform the development of culturally sensitive social media literacy programs and guide recommendations for healthy online behaviors across different cultures

Conclusion

This review explored the multifaceted impact of social media on young adults, particularly those navigating unresolved emotions from romantic relationships. Social comparison theory illuminates how curated online portrayals and algorithms fuel upward comparisons and potentially exacerbate anxiety and depression. However, gaps exist in understanding the broader impact on self-concept and social efficacy, as well as the potential influence of downward social comparison and cultural variations. The limited research on social media literacy interventions and platform-specific effects highlights the need for further exploration. Future studies should adopt a multi-dimensional and cross-cultural approach to gain deeper insights into the psychological ramifications of social media engagement. By addressing these identified gaps, researchers can pave the way for potential solutions that mitigate the negative effects and empower young adults to navigate the complexities of online environments.

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